

PROBABILISTIC JUSTIFICATION OF COMPOSITE AIRFRAME IN-SERVICE INSPECTIONS

Martin Gaitonde¹

¹Airbus Operations Ltd, Pegasus House, Aerospace Avenue, Filton
Email: martin.gaitonde@airbus.com, web page: <http://www.airbus.com>

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ABSTRACT

Airworthiness regulations for large civil transport aircraft require composite structures to be damage tolerant. A key aspect is to ensure sufficient residual strength throughout the service life of the aircraft despite the possibility of damage during operation. A maintenance activity is therefore needed for damage tolerant structure to allow inspection and follow-up actions (e.g. repair if damage is found), to ensure continued airworthiness.

Composite structures have good resistance to fatigue and environmental degradation. Accidental impact damage occurring during operation is the main focus for damage tolerance justification. This is different to metallic structures for which fatigue and fracture mechanics assessments can be used to confirm in service inspection programmes.

So an approach was developed to verify consistency of in service inspection tasks with the composite damage tolerance justification. It couples the usual damage tolerance stress margins, generated as part of certification, with a probabilistic analysis that accounts for the random nature of the accidental damage threat to which structures are exposed in-service. The probabilistic analysis exploits data such as: the impact threat to which the structure is exposed in service; residual strength as a function of damage severity; inspection effectiveness (detection capability and frequency). A practical way to verify compatibility of damage tolerance capability with the in-service inspection programme was therefore established. Some typical results are presented and the influence of residual strength capability on the interval is discussed.

The approach has been used within the MSG-3 analysis process for inspection programme definition for A380 and A350.

1 INTRODUCTION

The airworthiness regulation CS 25.571 entitled “Damage tolerance and fatigue evaluation of structure” states: “*An evaluation of the strength, detail design, and fabrication must show that catastrophic failure due to fatigue, corrosion, or accidental damage, will be avoided throughout the operational life of the aeroplane.*”

This regulation identifies limit load capability as a minimum residual strength for damage tolerant structures. It is applicable to both composite and metallic airframes, even though the approaches used to show damage tolerance are different. It is well known that damage tolerance justification for metallic airframes is based on assessment of crack initiation and propagation due to repeated loads i.e. primarily to address a fatigue phenomenon. Composite structures show good resistance to fatigue. Instead accidental damage is the main focus of the damage tolerance justification. Several types of accidental damage could occur due to a variety of sources. The most significant risk is that caused by potential in-service impacts, because the resulting damage (e.g. delaminations) may significantly affect residual strength. This damage may not be readily detectable, without dedicated inspection. Hence, damage tolerance assessment for composite structures focuses on the need to ensure residual strength in spite of the threat of in-service impact damage. A probabilistic approach is appropriate for this assessment because accidental damage is random in nature. It is used to verify consistency of the damage tolerance capability of the structure with the intervals selected for in-service inspection. It follows the underlying principle:

*The larger the strength reduction due to damage AND
the higher the probability of damage occurrence
→ The sooner the damage should be detected*

2 MAINTENANCE PROGRAMME DEFINITION FOR COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

2.1 MSG-3 Process

The Maintenance Steering Group (MSG-3) analysis process is applied to define an aircraft inspection programme. It includes inspections for Structural Significant Items (SSIs) i.e. those damage tolerant items which are justified to the requirements of CS 25.571. The process establishes inspections to ensure continued airworthiness accounting for possible in-service damage, whether fatigue, accidental or environmental damage. The composite damage tolerance assessment justifies the inspection programme against accidental damage within the MSG-3 process.

The initial definition of composite inspection tasks (i.e. the “basic requirement” per MSG-3) is defined considering maximum “likely” damage i.e. maximum damage that may typically occur once in the lifetime of the aircraft. The level of likely damage is defined by experience and with data such as the impact threat statistics used for the damage tolerance justification, whereby “likely” is considered to have an occurrence probability of 10^{-5} per flight hour (/FH). So for this fixed probability of damage occurrence, the basic inspection interval is established following a simplification of the previously mentioned principle, i.e.

*The larger the strength reduction due to damage
→ The sooner the damage should be detected*

The Static Strength Reduction (SSR) is a metric for the residual strength (in terms of Limit Load, LL, capability) associated to the “likely” damage and a corresponding basic inspection interval. Table 1 shows the relationship between the SSR, residual strength and basic inspection interval.

SSR	Strength	Severity of Damage	Basic Inspection
0	$\geq 1.5LL$	NEGLIGIBLE	No specific inspection task
1		VERY SLIGHT	12 years
2		SLIGHT	6 years
3		MODERATE	3yrs (A written remark must be provided)
4		SEVERE	< 3yrs (Predominant damage must be obvious damage for walk-around)

Table 1: SSR and associated basic inspection interval.

2.2 Damage Tolerance Philosophy

The Airbus damage tolerance philosophy for composite structures is shown in Figure 1. It has been presented previously by Fualdes [1].

Figure 1: Damage tolerance domain limits.

Static justification for composite airframes accounts for a level of impact damage shown by the yellow domain in Figure 1. Impacts which cause damage less than or equal to the limit of detectability associated to the in-service inspection programme are considered. This detectability threshold is known as Barely Visible Impact Damage (BVID). Only impacts with probability of occurrence up to 10^{-5} per flight hour are included in the static justification.

For composite structures, visual inspections are used to find any surface damages or cues to possible internal damage, knowing that accidental in-service impacts could result in delamination that is not directly visible. Therefore if surface damage is found, ultrasonic inspection is needed to check whether any internal damage is present.

There are two types of visual inspection normally used:

- General visual inspection (GVI) is a careful visual examination of relatively large areas of internal and/or external structure, usually carried out within touching distance.
- Detailed visual inspection (DET) is a close-proximity, intense visual inspection of relatively localized areas of internal and/or external structure. Inspection aids and techniques may be more sophisticated than for GVI (e.g. lenses, grazing light on a clean element).

GVI is more suited, than DET, to large areas. Hence, it can be less efficient to apply DET for frequent inspection of large areas. However, the advantage of DET is that it has the potential to detect smaller damages, due to the more intensive nature of the inspection.

The size of damage (BVID) assumed in the static justification, is relevant to the selection of inspection technique in that it is necessary to ensure a selected technique (DET or GVI) is capable of finding damage, which could reduce the airframe below ultimate load capability.

The detectability of dents due to impact on composite structures (e.g. Figure 2) has been investigated. A BVID threshold has therefore been defined for GVI, and another for DET, which represents the minimum damage size (dent depth) that can be reliably detected.

Figure 2: Impact perpendicular to a plane surface

The damage tolerance assessment to show compliance with CS 25.571 is conducted for damages that are greater than those considered in the static demonstration. The blue region of Figure 1 defines this damage tolerance domain. Two thresholds are defined as logical limits of the damage tolerance domain:

- a detectability threshold above which damage becomes readily detectable within a few flights: Large Visible Impact Damage (LVID) – see example in Figure 3,
- a severity of impact corresponding to an extremely improbable event ($\leq 10^{-9}$ per flight hour).

Figure 3: Example of readily detectable damage for a sandwich structure

Aircraft structure inspections are conducted in service and at intervals (say, 6 or 12 years) verified via the structure justification. The interval applied is confirmed in terms of both:

- Residual strength, and
- Repeated loads (i.e. fatigue loads).

The residual strength justification involves a probabilistic approach which accounts for the probability of damage occurrence and the probability of loads occurring that could cause failure with the assumed damage.

It is used to show that failure is extremely improbable considering the residual strength of the airframe accounting for the probability of undetected damage existing for a period of operation. For damages that are detectable, the period of operation is associated to the inspection interval. However, if the damage is undetectable (e.g. for thick structures), the damage tolerance justification (repeated loads and residual strength) covers the full life of the airframe.

Adequate residual strength must be ensured accounting also for the effect of repeated loads linked to the above mentioned period of operation. Testing is used to verify a philosophy of “no detrimental growth” for the damages considered in the damage tolerance justification.

2.3 Maintainability

A reduced maintenance burden can be realised for composite airframes with respect to that of traditional metallic airframes. However, direct comparison of maintainability for a metallic airframe with a composite airframe is not straightforward knowing the different drivers for the damage tolerance maintenance programme (fatigue damage for metal, accidental impact damage for composite).

The SSR (see section 2.1) can be a useful metric to help composite airframe designers provide maintainability improvements against metallic airframes. This is because it provides a link between residual strength (which can be established by the Stress Office) and maintenance burden for an airframe, which is associated to the difficulty and frequency of inspection. Furthermore the difficulty and frequency of repair can also be considered knowing that structural repair will be needed if damage occurs, which reduces the residual strength of the airframe below ultimate load capability.

3 PROBABILISTIC APPROACH

3.1 Residual Strength: Requirement

A semi-probabilistic approach is used to validate the inspection interval for finalisation of the Stress Office input to the MSG-3 process. Residual strength is assumed to be a deterministic function of impact energy. The formulation is similar to that described in section 12.2.4.2 of [2] and is based on the ATR72 approach [3].

The theoretical basis is developed as follows:

The probability of failure (P_{fail}) must be extremely improbable. Hence,

$$P_{fail} = P_{exist} \times P_{Load>RS} < 10^{-9} \text{ (per flight hour)} \quad (1)$$

where:

P_{exist} is the probability of at least one accidental damage existing at the flight preceding an inspection (or end of service life for undetectable damage), and

$P_{Load>RS}$ is the probability of occurrence of a load greater than the residual strength of the structure.

The probability P_{exist} is related to both the probability of occurrence of damage and the exposure time for structure in operation while containing potentially undetected damage:

$$P_{exist} = 1 - (1 - P_{occ})^{Int} \approx P_{occ} \times Int \quad (2)$$

where “Int” is the inspection interval for detectable damage (i.e. \geq BVID), or full service life for undetectable damage.

The probability of damage occurrence per flight hour, P_{occ} , is quantified as an “impact threat” to which the airframe is exposed in service. The impact threat used by Airbus has been validated by considering damage records for existing aircraft, as shown in extensive surveys:

- A survey on wing impact damage, covering all Airbus types, totalling 18,740,000 flight hours and 9,800,000 flight cycles
- A similar survey extended the data to the fuselage, covering A320 family, totalling 1,140,000 flight hours
- A similar survey covering the whole aircraft covering A320 family, totalling 500,000 flight hours
- An additional survey, totalling 10,330,000 flight hours

These data have been processed to identify severity and frequency of impact damages. Metallic structures provided a useful source of data for dents occurring in service and calibration laws were developed by impacting metallic test specimens e.g. A320 static test wing and coupons. This allowed estimation of impact energies for the damages identified through the surveys.

The following function to define impact threat was found to be suitable for justification of A380 composite structures:

$$P_{occ} = 10^{-3 - Eo/15} \text{ (rate per flight hour)} \quad (3)$$

where P_{occ} is the probability of occurrence of impact with energy exceeding Eo (units for $Eo = J$).

Ultimate load and other loads above limit load do not have a probabilistic definition in the airworthiness regulations (ref. CS 25), which are oriented to deterministic structure justification. However, to enable the probabilistic justification a log-linear law is assumed to represent the probability of occurrence of loads between limit load and ultimate load (1.5xlimit load). The probability of occurrence of “limit load” is assumed to be 10^{-5} per flight hour, whereas the probability of occurrence of “ultimate load” is assumed to be 10^{-9} per flight hour.

So the probability of occurrence of a load greater than residual strength ($P_{Load>RS}$) is:

$$P_{Load>RS} = 10^{3-8k} \text{ (per flight hour)} \quad (4)$$

where k is a factor on limit load, i.e. residual strength = k.LL ($1.0 \leq k \leq 1.5$), therefore

$$P_{fail} = (Int \times P_{occ}) \times 10^{3-8k} < 10^{-9} \text{ per flight hour} \quad (5)$$

For the limiting case $P_{fail} = 10^{-9}$ per flight hour, a residual strength requirement, k x LL ($1.0 \leq k \leq 1.5$), is defined as:

$$k = 1.5 + 0.125 \times \log (Int \times P_{occ}) \quad (6)$$

3.2 Residual Strength: Capability

Static strength of an airframe is justified as part of aircraft certification. Structure capability is evaluated by analysis, in terms of Reserve Factor (RF) where

$$RF = \text{allowable load} / \text{applied load (ultimate)} \quad (7)$$

This approach is applied for all possible failure modes, including those associated to residual strength after impact in which case the “allowable load” is the capability of the structure containing BVID (up to 10^{-5} per flight hour event, see Figure 1).

Equation 7 can be used to develop a relationship for the residual strength after impact of energy associated to the static justification (E_{static}) as follows:

$$\text{Residual strength after impact of energy } E_{static} / \text{ultimate load} = RF_{static} \quad (8)$$

It will be useful to express this in terms of limit loads i.e. same basis as for residual strength requirement (k x LL). This is done using the relationship: ultimate load = 1.5 x limit load.

$$\text{Residual strength after impact of energy } E_{static} / \text{limit load} = 1.5 \times RF_{static} \quad (9)$$

Testing on a range of composite materials used by Airbus has shown that residual strength capability as a function of impact energy follows a power law i.e.

$$(\text{Residual strength after impact}) \propto 1 / (\text{impact energy})^b \quad (10)$$

Equations 9 and 10 can be used to develop a relationship for the residual strength after impact of energy (E_j) greater than that considered in the static justification:

$$\text{Residual strength after impact of energy } E_j / \text{limit load} = 1.5 \times RF_{static} / (E_j / E_{static})^b \quad (11)$$

3.3 Interval Definition

To ensure that failure is extremely improbable across the range of impact energies to be considered within the damage tolerance domain, it is necessary to ensure that residual strength requirement (equation 6) never exceeds the residual strength capability (equation 11).

Figure 4 shows an example of this comparison for a range of energies between E_{static} and E_{LVID} , for a limiting case which defines the minimum acceptable inspection interval. This limit exists where the curve representing the residual strength capability just touches, but not does not go below, the line representing the residual strength requirement.

In this example, the range of energies to be considered has an upper limit (E_{LVID}), knowing that larger damages are not considered in the damage tolerance justification because they will be detected within a few flights.

Figure 4: Residual strength compatibility with requirement based on Failure Probability

Using this approach it was possible to calculate the minimum acceptable inspection intervals based on just 3 key inputs, associated to points 1 and 2 shown in Figure 5:

- Point 1
 - E_{static} (BVID up to 10^{-5} per flight hour event)
 - RF_{static} (vs UL and associated to structure containing impact damage due to E_{static})
- Point 2
 - E_{LVID} (up to damage tolerance cut-off energy, extremely improbable event)

Note that the probabilistic approach covers the damage tolerance domain (anywhere in blue region e.g. point 3), including the boundaries (points 1 and 2).

Figure 5: Identification of E_{static} (point 1) and E_{LVID} (point 2)

Typical results are shown in Figures 6 and 7, considering 2 different values for E_{static} i.e. 25J and 35J. Such data can be used to validate the inspection interval to ensure adequate residual strength.

Figure 6: Inspection interval as a function of RF_{static} and E_{LVID} for $E_{static} = 25J$

Figure 7: Inspection interval as a function of RF_{static} and E_{LVID} for $E_{static} = 35J$

4 DISCUSSION

The residual strength requirement (per equation 6) is not strongly influenced by interval e.g. a halving of inspection interval reduces the residual strength requirement (value of k) by less than 0.04. This is a consequence of the assumed probabilistic definition of load occurrences greater than limit

load. Conversely, values for inspection interval increase significantly as RF_{static} increases. This is due to the improved residual strength after impact (per equation 11), which then has a strong effect on calculated interval per equation 6.

While figures 6 and 7 look very different, it is possible to see them both as parts of the same carpet plot. For example, the interval values for a value of RF somewhat higher than the maximum shown in figure 6 ($E_{static} = 25J$) correspond to values for $RF = 1.00$ shown in figure 7 ($E_{static} = 35J$).

It is possible to construct a chart similar to Figure 1 using equation 6 showing the required residual strength factor k , as a function of probability of damage occurrence. An example of this sort of chart is shown in Figure 8. This figure shows required residual strength factor k for damages within the damage tolerance domain. Note that in this case “Int” is assumed to be a typical large civil transport aircraft scheduled inspection interval (36000 flight hours), or a service life of 140000 flights hours (when considering undetectable damage).

Figure 8 Residual strength requirements within damage tolerance domain for 36000 FH interval and 140000 FH service life

Figure 8 indicates that higher levels of residual strength are required for structure containing lower energy damage as these occur more frequently (per impact threat definition, equation 3). This can occur for thin sandwich structure. However, in that case there is little difference in the impact energy required for BVID in comparison to the impact energy required to create a readily detectable damage. So for such structures, the damage tolerance domain (between E_{static} and E_{LVID}) can be so small that adequate residual strength is ensured by the static demonstration. Indeed, for some thin composite A380 structures it was found that there was sufficient robustness to show ultimate load capability for readily detectable damage (LVID equivalent to BVID), such that no scheduled inspection is needed.

It is therefore evident from Figure 8 that the probabilistic approach gives residual strength compatible with the usual damage tolerance policy (Figure 1). This is a consequence of the exposure times (inspection interval or design life) for a large civil transport aircraft. However for airframes with shorter exposure times, there could be a benefit in defining requirements based on a probabilistic approach, because the probability of accidental damage existing is clearly related to the exposure time.

The following observations are also evident from Figures 6 and 7:

Values for inspection interval increase as E_{static} increases. This is because the damage tolerance justification is then addressing damages of lower probability of occurrence, such that the required residual strength k (per equation 6) is lower.

Lower values of E_{LVID} tend to improve the Interval. This is because a smaller range of energies is considered for the damage tolerance domain, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Effect of E_{LVID} on results of probabilistic approach

5 CONCLUSIONS

An efficient capability to validate inspection tasks for Airbus composite structures now exists. This has evolved from the approach used for ATR72 and that mentioned in CMH-17-3G. It involves a probabilistic analysis to show compatibility of the inspection programme with the results of structural analysis in compliance with the airworthiness regulation CS 25.571.

The quality of the input data required to establish the justification is of key importance. Airbus has advanced stress analysis approaches matured through decades of testing, analysis and justification of certificated composite aircraft structure. Furthermore, the impact threat definition has been derived using feedback from in-service Airbus aircraft. This makes the results very specific to the Airbus fleet. Nevertheless, the principle of the probabilistic justification approach can be applied generally for composite airframe damage tolerance justification to confirm in-service inspection intervals. So the damage tolerance principle (i.e. the link of structure justification to in-service inspection) is enacted for composite structures using a probabilistic approach, in contrast to the well-known enactment for metallic structure using deterministic fatigue assessment and fracture mechanics.

This new approach has been used to support the MSG-3 process for A380 and A350 composite structures.

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